

Effect of 5-Hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Juglone) on Morpho-physiological and Biochemical Aspects of *Cassia occidentalis* L.

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ABSTRACT

The present laboratory experimental study was carried about to evaluate the allelopathic potential of an allelochemical, 5-Hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Juglone) on some morpho-physiological and biochemical parameters of *Cassia occidentalis*. 1, 2, 5 mM concentrations of Juglone were applied to determine their effect on morpho-physiological parameters (seed germination, root length, shoot length, fresh weight, dry weight etc.) and biochemical parameters (chlorophyll, carotenoids, protein and α -amylase) of test plant under laboratory condition. Study was conducted on 10 day seedlings of *Cassia occidentalis*. Not only seedling growth parameters even the chlorophyll, carotenoids, protein and α -amylase were appreciably reduced, thereby indicating that Juglone negatively affects the growth of *Cassia occidentalis*. The study was concluded that Juglone possesses weed suppressing ability.

Key words: Allelopathy, Allelochemical, Weed, Juglone, *Cassia occidentalis*

INTRODUCTION

Weeds are unwanted and undesirable plants that interfere with the utilization of land and water resources and thus, adversely affect crop production and human welfare. Weeds compete with crop plants for nutrients, soil moisture, space and sunlight (Rajan and Sankaran, 1974). The world food loss due to weeds has been estimated to be about 11.5 percent of the total food production (Parker and Fryer, 1975). Among the natural plant

products, the allelochemicals create one of the major groups and provide allelopathic property to the donor plant, being biologically active. The allelopathic interactions, in general, and the allelochemicals, in particular, are regarded as an important tool for sustainable weed and pest management, and disease control (Singh *et al.*, 2001). The purified allelochemicals and /or their derivatives and even the compounds synthesized on their chemistry can be utilized as novel agrochemicals for sustainable management in an eco-friendly manner (Singh *et al.*, 2001). Growth of strawberry plant was inhibited strongly vegetatively as well as reproductively by the treatment of both juglone and undiluted walnut leaf extracts (Ercisli *et al.*, 2005). The length of roots and shoots of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) and peas (*Pisum sativum* L.) decreased in proportion to the increase in the concentration of aqueous extract isolated from walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) leaves (Maksimovic and Hasanagic, 2022).

Materials and Methods

Seeds of *Cassia occidentalis* were collected locally from wildy growing area of Distt. Muzaffarnagar. 5-Hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Juglone) was purchased from Sigma-aldrich, Germany.

Seeds were surface sterilized with 0.1% mercuric chloride. Seeds were dipped in distilled water for 24 h for imbibition prior to germination trials. These were then equidistantly placed in normal size petri dishes lined with two layers of moistened Whatman no.1 filter paper. The filter paper was treated with 1, 2, 5 mM (T₁, T₂ and T₃ respectively) of 5-Hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Juglone). For each treatment three replicates were kept. A similar set up of three replicates without treatment served as control (T₀).

The entire set up was kept in an environmentally controlled seed germinating chamber at 25⁰C and 75 % relative humidity with a photoperiod of 16/8 day/night. After 10 days, the number of seeds that germinated was counted, root length, shoot length, seedling fresh weight and dry weight were measured and the total chlorophyll, total carotenoids, total protein and α -amylase activity were estimated.

Results and Discussion

Morpho-physiological attributes of *Cassia occidentalis* were recorded in terms of % germination, root and shoot length, fresh and dry weight, vigour index, tolerance index and germination speed in different treatments of juglone. It is very clear from the results that in response to different concentrations of Juglone, Germination was considerably reduced in compared to control (Fig.1). Reduction in germination was more at 5 mM as compared to others. At the lowest concentration of 1 mM juglone treatment, germination was reduced by about 2.6% while at 2 mM, a reduction of over 15% was observed. A appreciable inhibition of germination of the test weed was observed at a concentration of 5 mM. The root length and shoot length of the test weed was significantly reduced and a significant reduction was observed (Fig.1). The fresh weight of test weed was slightly increased at 1 mM conc. but significantly reduced in 2 mM and 5 mM (13.7% and 33% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.1). Similarly dry weight was slightly increased at 1 mM conc. but appreciably reduced at 2 mM and 5 mM conc.(9.8% and 18% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.1). In case of % moisture, a little reduction was observed at lower to higher conc. as compared to control (Fig.1). Vigour index, tolerance index and germination speed were also significantly reduced at different conc. as compared to control (Fig.1).

Table-1 Morpho-physiological attributes of 10 days old seedlings of *Cassia occidentalis* grown in different concentrations of Juglone

Treatment (mM)	% Germination	Root length	Shoot length	Fresh weight	Dry weight	% Moisture content	Vigour Index	Tolerance index	Germination speed
0	89.00±2.00	1.87±0.37	5.07±0.24	81.13±4.61	6.73±1.03	91.72	617.66	100	22.25
1	86.66±2.08	1.49±0.24	5.09±0.11	82.93±4.01	6.87±0.23	91.7	570.22	79.67	21.66
2	75.00±1.00	1.07±0.16	4.18±0.31	70±5.97	6.07±1.62	91.39	393.75	57.21	15
5	69.00±1.00	0.37±0.16	2.56±1.14	54.10±3.82	5.50±0.71	89.76	202.17	19.78	13.8

Biochemical attributes of *Cassia occidentalis* were recorded in terms of Chl.a, Chl.b, total chl., total carotenoides, total proteins and α -amylase activity. Chl.a was appreciably reduced at 1, 2 and 5 mM conc. (7%, 13% and 21% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). Chl.b was appreciably reduced at 1 mM and 2 mM (7% and 15% respectively) but a significant reduction (41%) was observed at 5 mM conc. as compared to control (Fig.2). Total chl. was appreciably reduced at 1, 2 and 5 mM conc. (7%, 14% and 30% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). Total carotenoides were slightly reduced at 1 mM conc. but significantly reduced at 2 and 5 mM conc. (23% and 26% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). Total protein was slightly reduced at 1 mM but a significant increase was observed at 2 and 5 mM conc. (14% and 34% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). α -amylase activity was slightly reduced at 1 mM conc. but significantly reduced at 2 and 5 mM conc. (32% and 40% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2).

Table-2 Biochemical attributes of 10 days old seedlings of *Cassia occidentalis* grown in different concentrations of Juglone

Treatment (mM)	Chl, a (mg/gfw \pm SD)	Chl, b (mg/gfw \pm SD)	Total Chl (mg/gfw \pm SD)	Total carotenoides (mg/g fw \pm SD)	Protein (mg casein eq./g fw \pm SD)	α -amylase (mg starch degraded/min/gfw \pm SD)
0	0.262 \pm 0.005	0.249 \pm 0.014	0.512 \pm 0.009	0.547 \pm 0.011	42.70 \pm 3.91	44.30 \pm 0.34
1	0.242 \pm 0.004	0.230 \pm 0.008	0.473 \pm 0.004	0.514 \pm 0.013	41.85 \pm 1.48	42.26 \pm 0.45
2	0.227 \pm 0.011	0.210 \pm 0.016	0.436 \pm 0.0060	0.417 \pm 0.015	48.68 \pm 2.56	30.02 \pm 0.46
5	0.207 \pm 0.018	0.147 \pm 0.001	0.354 \pm 0.018	0.401 \pm 0.006	57.22 \pm 3.91	26.56 \pm 0.52

Conclusion

It is clear from the present study that 5-Hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Juglone) has a potential to reduce the some morpho-physiological parameters as well as biochemical parameters (germination, early growth and development of the weed species and thus could prove very useful for future weed management programmes.

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